

METHODS OF INCREASING THE PHYSICAL FITNESS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Tursaotov Ali Eshmo`minovicn

Acting Associate Professor of the Department of Physical Education and Sports
of Nizomiy Tashkent State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10803036>

Summary. Physical education requires the repetition of movement skills. Dynamic stereotypes of the movement are formed only when it is repeated many times. For effective repetition, such a system is necessary in which the mastered movement is connected with a new one, in other words, the repetition process has the character of variability (changes in exercises, performance conditions, variety of methods, differences in form and content of exercises in general).

Key words: Visibility, comprehensibility, individuality, loading, methods, sense of movement, stereotype.

Резюме. Физическое воспитание требует повторения двигательных навыков. Динамические стереотипы движения формируются только при его многократном повторении. Для эффективного повторения необходима такая система, при которой освоенное движение связано с новым, иными словами, процесс повторения имеет характер вариативности (изменения упражнений, условий выполнения, многообразии приемов, различия по форме и содержанию). упражнений в целом).

Ключевые слова: наглядность, понятность, индивидуальность, нагрузка, приемы, ощущение движения, стереотип.

Rezyume. Jismoniy tarbiya hosil qilinayotgan harakat ko`nikmalarining takrorlanishini talab etadi. Faqat ko`p marta takrorlangandagina harakatning dinamik stereotiplari shakllanadi. Samarali takrorlash uchun shunday tizim zarurki, unda o`zlashtirilgan harakat yangisi bilan bog`lanib ketsin, boshqacha aytganda takrorlash jarayoni variativlik xarakteriga (mashqlarning o`zgarishi, bajarish sharti, metodlarning xilma-xilligi, umuman mashg`ulotlarning shakl va mazmunan farqi) ega bo`ladi.

**Kalit so`zlar:** Ko`rgazmalilik, tushunarlilik, individuallilik, yuklama, metodlar, harakat sezgisi, stereotip.

Taking into account the interest, talent, individual talent, mental and physical characteristics, cultural needs of school-aged children, it is a process aimed at the comprehensive development of children, taking into account the formation of moral norms, acquisition of life and social experience. Development of physical education of children of junior school age, search for new ways to

solve their problems, firstly, with the need to resolve the indicated conflicts, and secondly, the laws, methodological and technical methods of improving the process of physical fitness and mental development of the growing young generation. is carried out in connection with the need to study the conditions. The second of the 5 important initiatives put forward by our President is aimed at physical training of young people and creation of necessary conditions for them to show their abilities in the field of sports. Popularization of national sports among the youth of the republic. To increase the number of people regularly engaged in physical education and sports to 33% in 2026."¹

Physical activity of school-aged children mainly refers to physical changes during early childhood, comprehensive physical education of the growing young generation is carried out with the joint efforts of educational institutions, families, public organizations. Physical education is aimed at improving health, developing physical quality, improving the functional state of the body, preparing young people for work and defense of the Motherland. The environment surrounding children is changing. Simple, simple games have been replaced by gadget games. Development of mental, aesthetic and physical education of the child is becoming a priority.

Without denying their importance, it should be said that the child's time for active games, walks, communication with peers and people in the environment is getting less and less. Games and other types of children's activities, the imbalance between different types of games (active and inactive, separate and joint) have a negative effect on the health of children of primary school age, both on the quality of movement and on the level of development of organizational skills. finding the opposite.

At the same time, the absence of considerations about the need to target physical qualities from an early age in the tasks of physical education in an educational institution attracts attention. For the training group only, there is a specific mention of the desirability of improving agility, quickness, endurance and strength in the program. The body of children of primary school age has two important characteristics, and knowledge of them allows the school teacher to successfully solve the problems of education of physical qualities.

Walking, running, jumping, throwing, swimming is the simplest movement necessary for life in children of junior school age. Children learn these movements quickly, because their nervous system is highly flexible. Before

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", No. PF-60, dated 28.01.2022

giving exercises to students of junior school age, it is necessary to give them an understanding of the importance of those exercises, the technique of performing them, the rules of mobile games, and some elements of physical education.

In order to achieve this goal, they provide a wide range of educational material, which usually consists of physical exercises and action games.

The following didactic principles are used in the process of conducting physical education classes and giving reasons: systematicity and consistency; awareness, independence and creative activity; optimally combine visual, oral and practical methods of education; understanding and individual performance basis; unity of frontal, group and individual forms of education, principles of increasing requirements. They are very important conditions of pedagogy and represent the methodological laws of the single pedagogical process of education and training. The principle of systematicity and consistency is mandatory for the entire complex of activities used for the purposes of physical education (regime, training, formation of movement skills).

Systematicity consists of the continuity, regularity, planning of the physical education process during the entire period of preschool education, the clear consistency of physical education classes based on the mandatory alternation of loading and rest, the consistency, sequence, and interrelationship of the classes. Systematicity is manifested in the interaction and interdependence of knowledge, skills and abilities: For example, children's mastery of material allows them to rely on it and move on to mastering new material, and new material is mastered z in turn prepares children to know the next.

Every day at a certain time, systematic performance of various physical exercises, as well as training activities of children under education, according to their character, will train children in the established regime of health and education. When systematic training is stopped, a decrease in the level of functional capacity achieved during the breaks between them, and sometimes a regression of morphological indicators is observed. This is manifested in a decrease in the specific weight of active muscle tissue, changes in its structural components, and other negative manifestations.

Physical education requires the repetition of movement skills. Dynamic stereotypes of the movement are formed only when it is repeated many times. For effective repetition, such a system is necessary in which the mastered movement is connected with a new one, in other words, the repetition process has the character of variability (changes in exercises, performance conditions, variety of methods, differences in form and content of exercises in general). In

addition, repetition ensures long-term readaptation in the morphological and functional spheres. Based on them, physical qualities develop. The introduction of new stimuli into the formed dynamic stereotypes gradually decreases without drastic changes.

The further development of actions is related to the child's ability to show creative activity, his performance of creative tasks (independent mastering of exercises, creating his own version, inventing something new). Opening promising opportunities for creative activity, treating children's first initiatives with sincerity and attention, systematically encouraging the search for new things requires. The principle of optimally combining visual, oral and practical methods of education. Cognitive activity is the unity of the general approach of emotional cognitive processes with practice. These integral parts of cognition are interconnected in the process of learning to act.

However, their consistency is different depending on the assigned tasks: teaching children to act by showing and explaining; it can begin with the teacher's verbal explanation of the exercise and its implementation by the children. In that case, as in this case, the demonstrative model does not exclude thinking, and the explanation does not exclude the imagination of action. Thus, expressiveness of words and actions are inseparable, closely related components. Demonstration in physical education means a large-scale interrelationship of all indicators of external and internal analyzers that connect a person (child) with the external environment. All cognition begins with the emotional stage. The formation of movements is carried out in the interaction of receptors, first of all, visual, auditory and proprioceptive receptors. The interrelationship of various receptor indicators enriches the image of movement, provides a deep understanding of it while serving to form movement skills.

The basis of demonstrability in learning new movements is realized by very clearly showing the movements by the teacher. It is aimed at creating aesthetic perception, a clear vision of movement, a sense of correct movement and a desire to repeat the movement. Since comprehensive development of sensory organs is one of the tasks of physical education, it is possible to exercise for a purpose with the methods of activating perception systems and influencing them selectively.

Visibility is closely related to awareness: a task given orally is understood by a person, tested in practice by repeating the action. Senses, especially movement senses, play an important role in this. In addition, the

interrelationship of expressiveness and figurative words will be of great importance. This relationship is based on the child's life experience, his movement imagination and creates a clear movement image. The role of the word, which is important for direct demonstration, increases more and more according to the experience acquired by the child. Such connection of the indicated forms of visibility is determined by the emotional and logical stages of cognition: that is, the connection of the first and second signal systems. The principle of comprehensibility and individuality envisages taking into account the possibilities of the child's young characteristics and, in connection with this, assigning tasks that match his strengths.

It is necessary to observe this principle in the system of physical education of children, because the performance of various exercises directly affects the vital functions of the child's body, which is not yet strong, and excessive physical exertion can have a bad effect on health. The optimal level of comprehensibility is determined according to the age capabilities of the children and the level of difficulty of the tasks. Comprehension does not mean that there are no difficulties, but, on the contrary, it means that they can be successfully overcome by the physical and mental effort of the child. Intelligibility in the true sense is confirmed or denied by the supervision of a doctor-pedagogue, which is carried out with the use of pulsometry, chronometry, etc.

References:

1. "2022-2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida" O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni, 28.01.2022-yildagi PF-60-son
2. A.E.Tursaotov. Jismoniy tarbiya. Oliy ta'lim muassasalari uchun darslik. 2021-yil.
3. A.E.Tursaotov. General characteristics of the organization of continuous pedagogical experimental work. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 6 JUNE 2023
4. A.E.Tursaotov. (2022). Structure and long-term dynamics of competitive activity of professional basketball players. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 10, 202-204.
5. Турсаотов, А. Э. (2023). Роль педагогической практики в формировании профессиональной компетенции учителя физической культуры. PEDAGOGIK ISLOHOTLAR VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI, 3(1), 54-55.
6. Рустамов, Л. Х. (2013). Источники и этапы развития теории и методики физического воспитания. Педагогика и современность, (3), 69-76.

7. Maxkamdjanov, K. M., Nurmatov, F. A., Inozemseva, L. A., & Rustamov, L. (2008). Sport bayramlarini tashkil qilish va o'tkazish metodikasi. Darslik T.
8. Рустамов, Л. Х., Утанов, Т. А., & Нигманов, Б. Б. (2015). Назначение и задачи профессионально-прикладной физической подготовки будущих учителей. Молодой ученый, (11), 1476-1478.
9. Рустамов, Л. Х. (2013). Физическая культура и ее влияние на организм человека. In Актуальные вопросы современной науки (pp. 99-103).
10. Rustamov, L. (2022). TALABALARNING KASBIY FAOLIYATLARIDA SHAXSGA YO'NALTIRILGAN YONDASHUVNI AMALGA OSHIRISH. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1259-1262.
11. Рустамов, Л. Х., & Зайниддинов, Т. Б. (2013). Основные средства физической культуры и классификация упражнений. Педагогика и современность, (5), 137-140.

